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**The Effects of Social Prejudice and Glass Ceiling Syndrome
on The Career Development of Women Assuming
Leadership Positions in Management in Türkiye**

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of social prejudice and glass ceiling syndrome on the career development of women in management leadership positions in Türkiye. The basic starting point of this study is the organizational prejudices, gender-based discrimination and invisible barriers that women managers have to deal with. In this context, the study aims to determine the social, cultural and institutional barriers that women face while working in leadership roles and to evaluate how these barriers affect their leadership philosophies and decision-making processes. A survey was conducted to collect data from 50 women working in management roles in various sectors in Türkiye and a mixed methodology was used in the study with quantitative and qualitative techniques for analysis. In addition to open-ended questions, participants were given statements that could be answered on a 5-point Likert scale. Frequency analysis, thematic analysis and mean score calculations were used to evaluate the data. In addition to obtaining statistical data, this approach provided the opportunity to learn from women about the events they experienced while assuming leadership positions and also included solution suggestions offered by them. According to the findings of the study, female leaders face more obstacles in their careers due to social prejudices than their male counterparts. Many interviewees identified the glass ceiling syndrome as an unnoticed but powerful obstacle. The majority of participants said that because they were women, their leadership abilities were questioned more often and that they had to work harder than their male counterparts to be accepted in positions of responsibility. It was also found that women's achievements were not as well known or valued as those of men. However, there are encouraging indications that female leadership is being accepted and that gender-based discrimination is decreasing in some sectors. The theoretical contribution of this study is to comprehensively evaluate the prejudices against women in leadership roles in Türkiye and the existence of the glass ceiling syndrome, as well as its effects on women in leadership positions, within the context of gender and leadership theories. Subjects' suggestions were used to promote equal representation in the field of leadership. According to the participants' suggestions, mentoring programs that assist women in leadership roles, flexible working hours, childcare facilities, trainings focused on gender equality, and institutional policies prohibiting discrimination stand out. In this context, the aim of the thesis is to both contribute to academic literature and to provide guidance to institutions and policy makers on how to create more equitable and inclusive leadership environments.

Keywords: leadership, discrimination, glass ceiling syndrome

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Introduction

This study aims to investigate the effects of social prejudices and glass ceiling syndrome on the career development of women who assume leadership positions in the field of management in Türkiye. The study aims to evaluate the current conditions in management levels from a gender perspective by analyzing the effects of prejudice-based obstacles that women leaders encounter in their careers on their managerial decision-making processes. Leadership and management are important concepts that have been discussed in the world for many years and many theses have been put forward regarding their implementation. Kouzes and Posner define leadership as “motivating people to work together and inspiring them towards a common goal.” Leaders motivate people to reach a common goal, and also, successfully managing the change processes of the organization is possible with qualified managers in decision-making positions" (Demirel & Kışman, 2022, p. 30). There are basic characteristics expected from leaders to ensure the success of organizations. Kesimli (2013) defines superior leadership as leadership with characteristics such as being innovative, mediator, assistant, mentor, coordinator, analyst and task master. However, in addition to the leadership characteristics expected from women who assume leadership positions today, promotion in business life is not only limited to talent and education, but also directly related to social perceptions. "The fact that various responsibilities such as the roles assigned to women by society, women's rights, equality between women and men, work life, being a mother and wife, are gathered around women individuals; In addition to showing that women have many problems they face in daily life, it also reveals the richness of women's identity." (Sivrikkaya & Wolff, 2021) In line with the additional expectations based on the social perception that women face on their way to leadership positions, unequal conditions arise in assuming leadership positions in working life. According to the IPU-UN Women 2023 map, more women have participated in political decision-making processes around the world, but gender equality has not yet been achieved. According to this study, the rate of women leading countries is still unequal on a global scale, and women's representation in ministries is still low. When the political administration area is taken as a sample, according to the IPU-UN Women 2023 map, as of January 1, 2023, 11.3% of countries have women heads of state, while 9.8% have women heads of government (19 out of 193 countries). 10 years ago, these figures were 5.3% and 7.3%, respectively. Among all regions, Europe continues to have the highest number of countries where women's participation in politics is the majority. In Türkiye, according to the Women in Statistics by TÜİK, according to 2023 data, although the average length of education for women has increased over the years, it was 9.2 years in Türkiye

in 2022, 8.5 years for women and 10.0 years for men. The labor force participation rate of women with higher education degrees was 68.8%, while it was 85.1% for men. In addition, it was seen that the employment rate of women was less than half that of men, and the gender wage or earnings gap was in favor of men at all levels of education. The rate of women in senior and middle-level management positions who assumed leadership positions was 19.6%. The low representation of women in leadership roles stems from a systemic injustice phenomenon that stems from personal preferences as well as cultural, social, and institutional reasons. Although leadership theories in the literature emphasize that experience, education, and environmental factors shape leadership in addition to innate characteristics (Avolio and Yammarino, 2013; Northouse, 2019), social prejudices complicate this process for women. According to Eagly and Karau's (2002) Role Conformity Theory, women face prejudices because they are not suitable for leadership positions, and these prejudices lead to the perception that women's leadership abilities are inadequate. According to studies, women managers must work harder than men (Smith et al., 2018), their preferences are questioned more often (Heilman, 2012), and they are less appreciated despite being at least as talented (The Economist, 2025). According to TÜİK (2024) data, the rate of women in senior and mid-level management roles in Türkiye is only 20.6%. This rate also shows that women are not sufficiently represented in management roles. In addition to institutional obstacles, women leaders face personal and societal challenges such as being a mother, having to manage a family, and not having access to flexible working arrangements (Hoşgör, Hoşgör, & Memiş, 2016; Sivrikaya & Wolff, 2021). To understand these multi-layered challenges, the research conducted within the scope of the thesis was conducted to learn and obtain information directly from the experiences of women managers. Fifty women managers participated in the study, which used a mixed approach that included qualitative and quantitative methodologies; open-ended questions probed their ideas and experiences in depth, provided clues directly from the subjects' ideas for solution suggestions, and Likert-scale questions evaluated women leaders' perceptions on the subject. The data were analyzed using methods such as frequency distribution, thematic analysis, and average score calculations. The thesis was organized to provide direct answers to the research questions. The literature review in the first section addresses gender biases, glass ceiling syndrome, leadership theories, and how women are perceived as leaders. The assessment of the current status of women's access to leadership roles in Türkiye was made possible by using this theoretical framework. The characteristics of the survey study and the analysis of the participants' perspectives are presented in the findings section. The results of the study made it possible to test theories and evaluate how social biases affect women's leadership. In light of social biases

and glass ceiling syndrome, this study attempts to address the difficulties women face in obtaining leadership roles in Türkiye in order to make a theoretical and practical contribution. The need for institutional policies and social change tactics that will promote equal representation in accordance with the research results has been sufficiently demonstrated. It is possible for women to be more visible in leadership positions through both long-term structural improvements and individual achievements. In this context, the thesis aims to provide an intellectual contribution as well as to direct institutions, civil society organizations, and policy makers towards achieving gender equality.

Literature Review

Leadership is a complex and multifaceted concept that has been widely studied across various disciplines, including psychology, management, and social sciences. At its core, leadership involves the ability to influence, motivate, and guide individuals or groups toward achieving common goals (Northouse, 2019). Unlike management, which primarily focuses on maintaining order, efficiency, and organizational structure, leadership is often associated with vision, innovation, and change (Kotter, 2012). Although there are several theories suggesting that leadership is linked to innate characteristics, however, contemporary perspectives emphasize that leadership is a skill that can be developed through experience, education, and practice (Avolio & Yammarino, 2013). Charry (2012), noting that scholarly interest in leadership increased significantly during the early part of the twentieth century, identified eight major leadership theories. While the earlier of these focused on the qualities that distinguish leaders from followers, later theories looked at other variables including situational factors and skill levels. Although new theories are emerging all of the time, most can be classified as one of Charry's eight major types (Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015, p. 7):

"Great Man" Theory: Great man theories assume that the capacity for leadership is inherent, that great leaders are born, not made. These theories often portray leaders as heroic, mythic and destined to rise to leadership when needed. The term great man was used because, at the time, leadership was thought of primarily as a male quality, especially military leadership (See also, Ololube, 2013).

Trait Theory: The trait theory of leadership evolved from suggesting only a select few were born to lead to predicting a leader's performance based on their personality traits (Harvard Law School Program on Negotiation, 2023).

Contingency Theories: Contingency theories of leadership focus on particular variables related to the environment that might determine which style of leadership is best suited for a particular work situation (Charry, 2012). Contingency theory states that effective leadership depends on the degree of fit between a leader's qualities and leadership style and that demanded by a specific situation (Lamb, 2013).

Situational Theory: The situational leadership model enables a leader to identify a task, set goals, determine the task maturity of the individual or group, select an appropriate leadership style, and modify the style as change occurs (Waller et al., 1989). this model defines three core

competencies of a situational leader: diagnosis, flexibility and partnering for performance (Blanchard et al. 2003, ss. I3–I5).

Style and Behaviour Theory: The style theory emphasizes the importance of specific leadership skills that enable a leader to act effectively while considering their previous capabilities. It suggests that each individual has a unique leadership style with which they feel most comfortable. Just as one size does not fit all, a single leadership style cannot be effective in every situation. Yukl (1989) introduced three distinct leadership styles. Employees working under democratic leaders exhibited high levels of satisfaction, creativity, and motivation. They worked with enthusiasm and energy regardless of the leader's presence and maintained better relationships with them, ultimately leading to higher productivity. In contrast, autocratic leaders focused primarily on maximizing output quantity (Nawaz & Khan, 2016).

Participative Theory: Participative leadership theories suggest that the ideal leadership style is one that takes the input of others into account. Participative leaders encourage participation and contributions from group members and help group members to feel relevant and committed to the decision-making process. A manager who uses participative leadership, rather than making all the decisions, seeks to involve other people, thus improving commitment and increasing collaboration, which leads to better quality decisions and a more successful business (Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015, as cited in Lamb, 2013).

Transactional Theory: The leadership theories, by the late 1970s and early 1980s, activated to diverge from the specific perspectives of the leader, leadership context and the follower and toward practices that concentrated further on the exchanges between the followers and leaders. The transactional leadership was described as that in which leader-follower associations were grounded upon a series of agreements between followers and leaders (House & Shamir, 1993, as cited in Nawaz & Khan, 2016).

Relationship/Transformational Theory: Relationship or transformational leaders motivate and inspire people by helping group members see the importance and higher good of the task. These leaders are focused on the performance of group members, but also on each person to fulfilling his or her potential. Leaders of this style often have high ethical and moral standards (Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015, as cited in Charry, 2012). Transformational leadership significantly influences the organizational environment by fostering a culture of trust, innovation, and shared vision. Leaders who exhibit transformational qualities, such as

idealized influence and intellectual stimulation, inspire employees to exceed expectations and engage in continuous learning (Bass & Avolio, 1994, as cited in Khan, 2023).

Skills Theory: This theory states that learned knowledge and acquired skills/abilities are significant factors in the practice of effective leadership. Skills theory by no means refuses to acknowledge the connection between inherited traits and the capacity to lead effectively, but argues that learned skills, a developed style, and acquired knowledge, are the real keys to leadership performance. A strong belief in skills theory often demands that considerable effort and resources be devoted to leadership training and development (Wolinski, 2010, as cited in Amanchukwu, Stanley, & Ololube, 2015).

One may assume that all managers are leaders, but that is not correct since some of the managers do not exercise leadership, and some people lead without having any management positions. Therefore, there is continuing controversy about the difference between leaders and managers. Some scholars argue that although management and leadership overlap, the two activities are not synonymous (Bass, 2010) Leadership and management entail a unique set of activities or functions. While leaders and managers share some similarities because they both influence others by using specific powers to achieve certain goals, there are also some prominent differences (Northouse, 2007). While managers maintain a smoothly functioning workplace, leaders test the current position and encourage new functions, so they are looking for long-term goals (Yukl, 1989). In today’s vigorous workplace, organizations need both effective management and effective leadership for optimal success (Kotterman, 2006).

Table 1: *Difference Between Leadersip and Management*

Leadership		Management
Focuses on people		Focuses on things
Articulates a vision		Executes plans
Trusts & develops		Directs & coordinates
Creates change		Manages change
Uses influence		Uses authority
Authority comes from personal relationships		Authority stems from position in the organization
Thinks strategically		Determines long-term objectives and strategies
Delegates responsibility		Acts decisively
Appropriate risk taking and innovation		Decides how to use personnel and other resources

Source: Azad et al. (2017, p. 102)

According to Eagly and Karau (2002) Men are more often characterized as “active”—that is, strong, controlling, and independent—while women are more often associated with “social” qualities that prioritize empathy and support for others. Men are seen as autonomous, dominant, and leadership-oriented, while women are expected to be sensitive, helpful, and compassionate. These are examples of gender roles. Research shows that there are still strong societal ideas that

men should be more active and women more collectivistic. (Eagly & Karau, 2002) This inequality places women at a structural disadvantage in leadership positions, given that leadership is often seen as a male domain. Perceptions of leadership are still influenced by gender stereotypes. These stereotypes often associate men with active qualities such as self-confidence, dominance, and assertiveness, while women are more strongly associated with social qualities such as empathy, collaboration, and nurturing. Women’s career success is further hindered by societal beliefs that women should focus on domestic duties while men should focus on their careers. Therefore, men are often seen as having a natural talent for leadership, while women must contend with more discrimination and scrutiny when demonstrating their leadership skills (Koburtay, Syed, & Haloub, 2019).

Bennis (1989) likened leadership to beauty, stating that it is difficult to define but you can recognize it when you see it. Because leadership is having a whole of capacities that are different, more diverse, more, more colorful, and deeper than any other person (Fındıkçı, 2012). Despite this, although it is hard to define, when we look at the studies that define the leader in literature, the characteristics that a leader should have been discussed more, and many studies have been done on this. The characteristics that should be possessed to be a successful leader are classified in the table below:

Table 2: *Characteristics That a Leader Must Have*

HAVING TEAM SPIRIT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using the Concept of ‘We’ - Not Discriminating Between Team Members - Having Management Skills
HAVING COMMUNICATION SKILLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Persuasion Skills - Presentation Skills - Empathy - Effective Listening and Speaking/Being Ready to Answer
HAVING HIGH MOTIVATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive Thinking - Being Satisfied with Your Job
COURAGE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being Patient - Enduring Difficulties - Taking Risks
HAVING SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Giving Importance to Social and Sports Activities - Providing Social Benefit - Being Sensitive to Human and Moral Values
BEING FORESIGHTED	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thinking Multi-Dimensional / Analyzing and Interpreting Events - Seeing Future Opportunities and Threats - Determining Future Strategy

SHOWING TARGETS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determining Tasks for the Goal - Being Clear and Explicit in Tasks - Making the Tasks Acceptable to the Audience - Creating Standards / Adhering to Standards Making up - Checking the Standard - Mentoring
HOLDING A VISION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International Perspective - Believing in the Vision/Devotion - Being Clear and Concise in the Vision - Focusing on a Single Point in the Vision
ADOPTING THE VISION TO THE AUDIENCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guiding and Encouraging the Audience - Making Efforts for Implementation - Integrating Individual Goals with the Goal of the Organization
INDIVIDUAL COMPETENCIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being Self-Confident/Assertive - Having Knowledge - Having Experience - Giving Importance to Entrepreneurship - Motherhood - Honesty/Transparency - Having Business Skills

Source: Şencan et al. (2015, p. 245)

Gallup found that 33% of Americans said they would rather work for a male management, 20% said they would rather work for a female manager, and 46% said they had no preference (Gallup, 2013). According to Örüçü (2007), the reasons for preferring a female boss are as follows;

- Women put in more effort and are more careful than men,
- Women can better provide the necessary training to employees.
- Women can adapt to changes more easily,
- Women's ability to encourage and motivate their employees is more developed than men,
- Women are more open to new ideas and more creative,
- Women can better transfer their observation skills to business life,
- They can communicate better with their employees,
- Women are more successful in solving problems,
- Women also have a clear strategy in business life (Örüçü, 2007).

In general, prejudice can arise from the relations that people perceive between the characteristics of members of a social group and the requirements of the social roles that group members occupy or aspire to occupy (Eagly, in press). A potential for prejudice exists when social perceivers hold a stereotype about a social group that is incongruent with the attributes that are thought to be required for success in certain classes of social roles. When a stereotyped group member and an incongruent social role become joined in the mind of the perceiver, this inconsistency lowers the evaluation of the group member as an actual or potential occupant of the role. In general, prejudice toward female leaders follows from the incongruity that many people perceive between the characteristics of women and the requirements of leader roles.

Perception of Leadership

To date, many definitions have been made, and theories have been put forward regarding what leadership really is. According to the data provided in the study by Şencan, İbicioğlu and Karabekir (2015), although leadership has been defined many times by different researchers, it is understood that leadership is a process related to influencing people for a specific purpose. The leader determines his/her strengths and weaknesses by knowing himself/herself and his/her group and then determines and carries out his/her goals and activities according to the possible opportunities and threats in the environment. Role Congruity Theory, developed by Eagly and Karau (2002), is one of the important theoretical frameworks explaining prejudice against women leaders. Role congruity theory is based on social role theory's consideration of the content of gender roles and the importance of promoting gender differences in behavior, the theory simply examines the fit between gender roles and other roles, especially leadership roles. It identifies the underlying factors and processes that influence perceptions of this fit in society, social prejudices in society, and the consequences for prejudicial behavior. Therefore, when men and women take on leadership roles, different evaluations and judgments may occur in the eyes of society. Sabancı University's (2020) study makes important points about the obstacles that female CEOs in management face in their careers. A recurring theme is that women are more likely than men to hesitate to take on new employment opportunities or promotions because they believe they must meet all the requirements before advancing in the company. On the other hand, men tend to be more confident in their abilities, even if they are not as talented in some areas. This self-imposed restriction, reinforced by social norms, can cause women to progress more slowly in their careers. Another finding from the interviews is that many women may not initially be aware of the gender-based obstacles they face in the workplace. However, as they reflect more and interact with other women in leadership roles, they often discover that

social and cultural traditions put more pressure on women, especially when it comes to balancing work and family obligations. Women face a “double burden” due to these systemic issues, making it difficult for them to compete on equal terms with their male counterparts (Sabancı University, 2020). In addition, all women who participated in the interview support a quota system to ensure that female leaders are elected under equal conditions and that equality in career development is ensured.

According to the research reported by Smith and Nikolov (2018), the words used to describe male and female leaders differ. The study, which included more than 4 thousand participants, examined objective and subjective performance criteria covering 89 positive and negative leadership adjectives used to evaluate leadership performance in the military.

- Use of positive adjectives for male leaders: Analytical, competent, athletic, reliable, self-confident, versatile, eloquent, rational, logical, practical.
- Use of positive adjectives for female leaders: compassionate, enthusiastic, energetic and organized.
- Use of negative adjectives for male leaders: arrogant, irresponsible.
- Use of negative adjectives for female leaders: incompetent, selfish, frivolous, passive, scattered, opportunistic, gossipy, excitable, self-conceited, easily panicked, unruly, indecisive.

According to the findings, managers use more positive words to describe men in performance evaluations, while choosing more negative ones to describe women. Prejudice affects women's career progression by reinforcing stereotypes that associate leadership with masculinity. Research indicates that "women in managerial roles face increased scrutiny and higher performance expectations than their male counterparts" (Heilman, 2012, p. 120)

Women in Leadership

According to Eagly and Karau (2002), women find it difficult to be seen as leaders because leadership positions are often associated with masculine characteristics. The degree of conflict between the leadership function and the female gender role depends largely on how the concept of leadership is defined. If these positions are associated with more “effective” (dominant, powerful, and autonomous) characteristics, women are less likely to be seen as qualified for leadership positions. On the other hand, if these positions are characterized by less macho and more communal characteristics, women are more likely to be seen as more suitable for leadership positions. This case illustrates how gender norms in leadership are constructed and

can make it difficult for women to hold positions of authority (Eagly & Karau, 2002). Women continue to be disproportionately burdened with caregiving responsibilities, limiting their ability to take on demanding leadership roles" (Hoşgör, Hoşgör, & Memiş, 2016). Women as less qualified than men should weaken or even disappear. To briefly touch upon the history of women and leadership, Şencan, İbicioğlu and Karabekir (2015) state the following: The concept of female leadership is encountered with striking examples in every period of history. However, despite these examples, women's leadership has been debated, and many ideas have been put forward about whether women can be leaders. In the Western tradition, Socrates emphasized that the more knowledge you have on a subject, the more authority you will have, by saying, "For example, in areas where women know more, such as spinning wool." However, Socrates did not comment on whether a woman who commands men in spinning wool could learn to command a warship (Adair, 2005: 280). On the other hand, throughout history, we have come across many female leaders in political and military fields. In fact, in many tribes and kingdoms, if the deceased king did not have a son, it was a law that the eldest daughter would ascend to the throne (Adair, 2005: 279). During the 93 War, Nene Hatun, who was only a 20-year-old bride, set an example for the local people with her determination and ambitious struggle on the battlefield, and she led them along, showing that there were female leaders in the military as a servant leader in our history. Another female leader who had her name written in gold letters in history was Marie Curie, who led women by winning the first Nobel Prize in science. (Fındıkçı, 2012: 428-429). Apart from these, we see many female leaders in politics, which is another area in history generally dominated by men. Sirimavo Bandaranaike, Indira Gandhi, Margaret Thatcher, Benazir Bhutto and Tansu Çiller have also gone down in history as the first female presidents of their countries and the world (Adair, 2005: 279; Çimen, 2012b: 272-273; Çimen, 2012a: 329-334; Çimen, 2012b: 329). This trend symbolizes the emergence of more female leaders in areas generally associated with men (Adair, 2005: 279). In this context, it has been seen that women can effectively take part in every area where men are present (p. 246). Women were able to become leaders in areas where men were leaders and did not face any personal obstacles in maintaining their leadership. Roles, actions, attitudes and characteristics that society expects from people may vary according to gender. Business life is also affected by these roles imposed by society. This effect emerges as gender discrimination. (Sivrikaya & Wolff, 2021, s. 65). "

According to Hoşgör, Gündüz Hoşgör, and Memiş (2016), female healthcare professionals face greater barriers in advancing to senior management positions compared to their male colleagues

Table 3: *Glass ceiling barriers*

Barriers from Factors	Stemming from Individual	Barriers from Organizational Factors	Stemming from Societal
1. Multiple Assumption	Role	1. Organizational Culture and Policies	1. Occupational Segregation
2. Women's Personal Preferences and Perceptions	and	2. Lack of Mentorship	2. Stereotypes and Prejudices
		3. Exclusion from Informal Communication Networks	

Source: Karaca (2007, as cited in Hoşgör et al., 2016, p. [348])

In the research conducted with healthcare professionals, the relationships and differences between the glass ceiling syndrome and the socio-demographic variables of the participants were investigated. According to the findings, since the sub-dimension of ‘Women’s Personal Preference Perceptions’ had the highest average, it can be interpreted that women build their own career barriers. On the other hand, the fact that ‘Stereotypical Prejudices’, which includes sexist approaches such as women not being as ambitious/hardworking as men and not making enough effort to be able to take part in management positions, has the second highest average can be evaluated as a quite remarkable result (Hoşgör, Gündüz Hoşgör & Memiş, 2016).

According to the World Economic Forum 2024 assessment, with a gender parity rate of 64.5% in 2024, Türkiye has one of the lowest percentages of gender parity among European countries. Compared to other European countries, Türkiye has one of the lowest percentages of female representation in senior management positions; women make up only 18.5% of senior management positions, while this rate rises to 42.4% in technical and professional disciplines. At the same time, despite a few exceptions, Europe is the only country out of 40 economies where the labor force participation rate for both men and women is less than 50% (49.2%). The "Women in Statistics" report published annually by the Turkish Statistical Institute provides detailed information on almost every situation of women. Leadership and women's participation

in the workforce can also be observed each year through this data. When looking at 2024 data, the rate of women in upper and middle management positions was 20.6%. According to the results of the household labor force survey, this rate, which was 14.4% in 2012, became 20.6% in 2023, and according to Borsa Istanbul data, when the board members of 50 companies traded here were examined, the rate of women members, which was 12.2% in 2016, became 19.4% in 2024. In the 2024-2028 action plan prepared by the General Directorate of the Status of Women (2024), concrete targets have been set to increase the participation rate of women in the workforce and strengthen their representation in leadership positions. According to the report, although the ratio of employees in public institutions in Türkiye is close to each other, the representation of women in leadership positions is not equal to that of men. According to the July 2023 data of the Presidency of Strategy and Budget, General Directorate of Budget, Public Personnel Information System Department, 86.51% of senior managers in the public sector are men and 13.49% are women. Of the total public employees, 42.10% are women and 57.90% are men.

Table 4: *Statistics of Women Managers in Public Sector*

Titles	Female Employees	Total Senior Employees	Percentage
Governor	3	81	3,70
General Manager	22	217	10,14
Deputy General Manager	52	403	12,90
Minister	1	31	3,23
Vice President	14	144	9,72
Head of Department	593	3.212	18,46
District Governor	102	1233	8,27
Regional Director	12	279	4,30
Deputy Regional Director	35	583	6
Total Senior	834	6183	13,49

Source: T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Hizmetler Bakanlığı, Kadının Statüsü Genel Müdürlüğü (2023)

Glass Celiling and Social Prejudice

Although women have gained increased access to supervisory and middle management positions, they remain quite rare as elite leaders and top executives. To explain this phenomenon, public and scientific discussion has centered on the idea of a “glass ceiling” a barrier of prejudice and discrimination that excludes women from higher level leadership positions (Federal Glass Ceiling Commission, 1995; Morrison, White, & Van Velsor, 1987). When the roles of leader and follower are examined, we see that women are mostly in the follower role. Woolf (1929, back cover)'s words "Throughout all these centuries, women have

served as a mirror that makes men look twice as big as they are, a magical mirror with a tremendous power of reflection" expresses the role of women as followers in supporting men's leadership (Fidan, 2019). Sivrikaya and Wolff (2021) define the glass ceiling as invisible but difficult to overcome barriers that prevent women from being promoted to senior management positions regardless of their achievements or abilities. Virginia Woolf points to this very issue when she says, "I believe that even when there is nothing to prevent a woman from becoming a doctor, lawyer, or civil servant, and all paths are open, there are still many obstacles and ghosts in her path" (Adair, 2005: 279). Although women have entered business life, there are still some barriers that prevent them from advancing in this arena and create problems in their reaching senior management positions. The "Glass Ceiling", defined as invisible barriers that prevent women from advancing beyond a certain level in management, is one of these barriers (Özyer& Orhan, 2012: 973)." While discussing the leadership trait approach, although physical traits such as age, height, weight, strength, and handsomeness are mentioned, no mention is made of traits that may belong to women such as beauty and likeability. Traits believed to be innate in male leaders are not sought in women (Sivrikkaya & Wolff, 2021). "When national and international studies on female executives are examined, it is observed that certain obstacles exist simply because they are 'women,' regardless of factors such as discipline, age, education level, or marital status (Çelikten, 2004). Women have been so excluded from management that even in teaching a profession commonly associated with women in Türkiye female administrators remain a minority (Tan, 1996)" (as cited in Fidan, 2019, p.57). A recent analysis by The Economist (2025) suggests that Among OECD countries, the Labor-force participation rate is 29th and the lowest in Türkiye. In 2024, women participated 37.3% less than men. In Italy, which is one step ahead of Türkiye, 28th, the rate is 18.1%. In terms of the proportion of women in management, Türkiye has been far behind since 2016, with Japan and South Korea ranking last among OECD countries in 2024. " The female labor force participation rate in Türkiye is one of the lowest among OECD countries, reflecting persistent structural barriers to women's economic empowerment" (Karatepe and Türkmen, 2025). According to the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap 2024 report, Türkiye ranked 129th out of 146 countries in gender equality with 63.8 percent. The share of women in senior leadership positions is 10 points lower than men with 32.2 percent. On the other hand, although the share of women in leadership positions has been increasing steadily for the last 8 years at 1 percent, this progress reversed in 2023. The glass ceiling effect is reinforced by workplace cultures that favor male-dominated leadership styles, making it harder for women to break through" (Mert, 2019). Women in leadership roles often have to work twice as hard as their male counterparts to gain

the same level of recognition and credibility" (Akbaş & Korkmaz, 2017). Despite higher education levels, women are still underrepresented in executive roles, showing that educational attainment alone does not overcome structural barriers" (Sivrikaya & Wolff, 2021). These invisible barriers stem from the male-dominated organizational culture and gender-based stereotypes" (Salik Ata, 2023). Women's leadership styles are different from men's, but both genders can learn from each other for effective leadership" (Yücel, 2022). Although female professionals have been more represented in companies in recent years, they are still not included in the top management of many large organizations" (HRdergi, 2025). "Examples of obstacles stemming from the perception of male managers include gender blindness, prejudices, protection instinct, communication difficulties, and the desire to hold on to power. Issues such as gender blindness and protection instinct also come to the fore in female managers, but in addition to these, the queen bee syndrome, the self-reference illusion, multidimensional jealousy, and the effort to appear like a man also support the glass ceiling perception. For this reason, 50-60% of women prefer male managers. A person may also create obstacles for themselves because they assign a role to themselves, adopt social values as they are, experience work-family conflict (feelings of guilt), lack self-confidence, lack desire, belief, and opportunities, do not care about their career, or avoid career challenges." (Gül & Oktay, 2009, p. 428)

Goals Related to Female Leadership Participation

Some plans and strategies have been developed globally and in Türkiye for women's participation in the workforce and their equal promotion to leadership positions. Although the developed strategies have been somewhat effective in women's career development, according to the most detailed research available, TÜİK Statistics on Women (2024), gender equality has not been achieved. According to the UN Women Strategic Plan 2022–2025, the organization's goals include increasing women's participation in the economy and society, helping them gain equal access to opportunities, and ensuring their equal access to resources. As part of the 2021–2025 Gender Equality Strategy, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) also wants to integrate a gender perspective into its projects and policy initiatives and strengthen assistance to promote equal opportunities for women. According to the Green Growth Platform, women's participation in the workforce and assuming leadership positions can also be associated with sustainability. The 17 goals, which entered into force in January 2016 and are targeted to be achieved by 2030, were adopted by 193 member countries of the United Nations in order to eliminate poverty, protect the planet Earth and ensure that all people

live in peace and prosperity. Article 5 of the Sustainable Development Goals was determined as ‘Achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls’. It was also stated that sustainability should not be considered only as climate change, but that its main purpose, when viewed from a broader perspective, is to leave a beautiful future for future generations in environmental, social and economic dimensions (Green Growth Platform, 2024). Developed with the financial support of the ILO Türkiye Office and the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA),⁵⁰ “MIG SCORE” aims to improve productivity, and therefore competitiveness, as well as working conditions in small and medium-sized enterprises, and to strengthen institutional change towards Gender Equality. In addition to training, one-on-one consultancy services are also provided to enterprises within the scope of the “MIG SCORE” program. It also focuses on the five most fundamental issues related to Gender Equality in working life: work-life balance, equal pay, equal pay for equal value, inclusive employment, working environment and good treatment (International Labour Organization, 2018). Mother Child Education Foundation (AÇEV) develops and implements educational programs for children, parents and young women in need across Türkiye. Carrying out various activities to increase social awareness, AÇEV focuses on quality education in early childhood, the role of families in raising future generations, gender equality and lifelong learning. According to Procter & Gamble (n.d.), achieving gender equality in business is a key factor in accelerating economic growth. P&G focuses on three areas where it can make the biggest impact: “advertising and media,” “education and economic opportunities,” and “an inclusive environment within P&G.” First, it uses its power in advertising and media to break down gender bias. The #SeeHer study by the National Advertisers Association of America shows that 40% of women are portrayed incorrectly through stereotyping, objectification, or degrading. It also works to remove barriers to education for girls and economic opportunities for women through corporate and brand programs and policy support. According to the 2024-2028 action plan published by the General Directorate of Women's Status of the Ministry of Family and Social Services of the Republic of Türkiye (2023), it is aimed to develop comprehensive policies in order to increase the effective participation of women in decision-making mechanisms. The Turkish Civil Code entered into force on January 1, 2002. According to the report, the regulations started with the amendments made to the constitution in 2004, and the provision "Women and men have equal rights. The State is obliged to ensure that this equality is put into practice" was added to Article 10 of the constitution in 2004. and in the women section of the Development Plan (2024-2028), the main objective was determined as "To ensure that women who have a central role in the family see the superior value they deserve

and to accelerate our development, to ensure that women benefit equally from opportunities and facilities in all areas of life, especially education and employment, and to live free from all forms of violence and discrimination, and to increase representation and participation in all areas and levels". The report has a separate section titled "Participation in leadership and decision-making mechanisms" and includes plans to develop the concept of women-leadership. Although Turkish women gained the right to vote and be elected in local elections in 1930 and the right to vote and be elected in parliamentary elections in 1934, women still need to be supported in the areas of administration and politics. According to the report, Türkiye lags the world in the number of women deputies.

Figure 1: *Female MP Rates in 2023*

Source: Eurostat (2023, as cited in T.C. Aile ve Sosyal Hizmetler Bakanlığı, Kadının Statüsü Genel Müdürlüğü, 2024, p. 134)

According to the United Nations Development Program (UNDP, n.d.), the aim is to support social cohesion between refugee and host communities in Türkiye through the empowerment of women. According to the December 2018 data of the General Directorate of Migration Management, Türkiye was hosting 3,622,366 Syrians under temporary protection status. Türkiye was the country hosting the largest refugee population in the world. The project aimed to ensure cohesion between the two communities, to develop the social and economic skills of Syrian and host community women, to design social care and social support services and to implement pilot applications, and to implement social care and social support services targeting women, disabled youth and the elderly to better reach the most vulnerable segments of the Syrian and host communities.

Research Findings

Demographic Information:

Although the quota for the survey was 100, it was completed by 50 participants. Considering the relatively small number of female managers in Türkiye and their willingness to participate in surveys, a smaller sample size could be appropriate given the nature and scope of the research. The study focuses on women in managerial roles in Türkiye, a relatively narrow and specific.

research sample. The data collected can be considered sufficient for the purpose of finding significant trends and making initial inferences, given the specialized nature of the sample and the difficulty of contacting this group within the research time limit. The validity of the results is further strengthened by the fact that the sample continues to provide a diverse demographic representation (in terms of age, education, sector, and experience). Therefore, although a larger sample size would allow for broader generalization, the current dataset provides valuable insights into the research questions and the analysis will be conducted accordingly and appropriate limitations will be discussed.

Figure 2: Age distribution of participants, n=50

Source: own data

The majority of the participants in the survey are female managers between the ages of 25 and 35. The fact that most of the participants are at the top of their careers can more clearly reveal the difference between expectations and challenges in the current order.

Figure 3: Educational level of participants, n=50

Source: own data

A smaller percentage of study participants had a master’s degree, while the majority had a bachelor’s degree. This suggests that the majority of the sample was comprised of mid-level professionals with a bachelor’s degree, consistent with the career stage in which many women are in management. The participants’ educational backgrounds, while not dominated by graduate degrees, represent a group with sufficient professional experience and academic expertise to provide important insights into gender and leadership dynamics.

Figure 4: Participants by employment sector, n=50

Source: own data

Most of the participants were people working in the private sector, with a small number of government employees showing interest in the survey. Although people working in government institutions were approached, most of them were not willing to fill out the survey. Although the survey did not require detailed information about the institution, this may be related to the reluctance of government employees to share any information about the institution they work

for. In addition, since the number of NGO managers was quite limited, a small sample size could be found.

Figure 5: Participants by management position level, n=50

Source: own data

The survey found that the majority of participants were women leaders working at the middle management level. This may suggest that middle managers are more open or approachable to participate in this type of study than more senior managers. Respondents whose roles did not fit neatly into the predefined categories were included in the “Other” category, indicating that participants had a variety of professional backgrounds. Compared to middle managers, the numbers of senior managers and specialist/civil servant positions were comparable, indicating a balanced but less significant presence. Nevertheless, a significant number of women managers working in senior management positions were captured.

Figure 6: Years in management, n=50

Source: own data

Respondents with 3-5 years of experience constitute the majority, followed by those with 1-3 years of experience. This means that early- and mid-career stage managers who are actively developing their leadership skills constitute most of the sample. A smaller group with more than ten years of expertise can provide long-term insights into organizational and structural issues. The views of a wide range of respondent profiles with almost different levels of expertise are reflected in the diversity of respondent responses.

Figure 7: Estimated number of female managers in participants' organisations, n=50

Source: own data

There is wide variation in the proportion of female executives in respondents' organizations. There is a reasonable representation of women in leadership positions, as most respondents indicated that they work in organizations with three to five female managers. However, some companies have a disproportionately high proportion of female executives (e.g. 80, 250, or even 600), indicative of a large-scale corporate or public sector environment. On the other hand, other companies claim to have one or no female executives, highlighting gender inequality in leadership across sectors.

The hypotheses and research questions in this area of the study are immediately addressed in detail in the section that follows. A distinct facet of social prejudices, gender-based discrimination, and their effects on women in leadership roles are covered in each topic.

The following hypotheses are to be tested by the analysis, which adheres to the research questions:

- **H1:** *Glass ceiling syndrome and social prejudice negatively impact women's ability to rise to management positions in Türkiye.*
- **H2:** *Women leaders in management positions in Türkiye face more obstacles based on social prejudice than their male counterparts.*
- **H3:** *Gender prejudices negatively affect the perception of women managers' competencies in leadership positions.*

In this section, each section of the survey aims to provide statistical data to test hypotheses and research questions.

1. Gender-Based Discrimination and Career Trajectories

Question 1: "How does gender-based discrimination in the workplace influence the career trajectories and leadership experiences of women in management?" and tests H1.

2. Social Prejudices and Glass Ceiling Syndrome

Question 2: "In what ways do social prejudices and the glass ceiling syndrome impact the career advancement opportunities of women in leadership positions?" and tests H1, H2.

3. Types of Social Prejudices and Leadership Styles

Question 3: "What types of social prejudices do women in leadership positions encounter throughout their careers, and how do these prejudices shape their leadership styles and decision-making processes?" and tests H3.

4. Social Prejudice-Based Obstacles vs Male Counterparts

Compares the frequency and severity of difficulties faced by male and female leaders in similar situations to provide a more thorough analysis of H2 and H3.

5. Solutions, Institutional Policies, and Recommendations

Provides qualitative information about possible organizational and social reforms that might lead to more women in leadership positions in Türkiye.

Gender-Based Discrimination and Career Trajectories:

-This section tests hypothesis H1

(Glass ceiling syndrome and societal prejudice negatively affect women's ability to advance to managerial positions in Türkiye.)

-Also related to Research Question 1

(How does gender-based discrimination in the workplace affect the career trajectories and leadership experiences of women in management?)

Figure 8: Perceived negative impact of gender on career advancement, n=50

Source: own data

The responses reveal a range of views on barriers to career progression based on gender. Although most participants (score 3) were neutral, a significant number (score 4) believed that their gender had a negative impact on their career progression. Direct experiences of gender-related barriers were reflected in the high level of acceptance by a smaller but significant group (score 5). However, some participants (scores 1-2) said that their gender did not significantly limit their career options. These results suggest that gender-based barriers to career progression may exist, but not all individuals perceive them in the same way. The findings highlight the need for more qualitative information to understand the specific contexts in which gender affects career development.

Figure 9: Barriers to compared to male colleagues, n=50

Source: own data

The responses of the participants indicate that a significant portion (scores 4 and 5) face more obstacles in the promotion process compared to their male counterparts. This result shows that gender-based obstacles affect the participants in their career progression. The participants who disagree with this view with scores (1-2) show that not all female managers experience discrimination in promotion to the same extent. The findings are consistent with the glass ceiling theory, which describes the structural difficulties women face when advancing to leadership positions. The results further emphasize the importance of institutional policies that promote gender equality in promotion processes.

Figure 10: Experiences of explicit or implicit gender-based discrimination in the workplace, n=50

Source: own data

The results highlight that some participants have experienced gender-based discrimination, either explicitly or implicitly, with ratings ranging from 3 to 5. However, a significant portion also scored within the 1 to 3 range, indicating that some participants have not personally experienced such a situation. This may vary depending on workplace cultures and the policies of the institutions they work in. The findings further support the claim that gender biases can be ingrained in professional environments, sometimes in ways that are not obvious but still affect career progression and leadership opportunities.

Figure 11: Perceived competence questioning in leadership appointments, n=50

Source: own data

Although responses varied, a significant number of participants who rated themselves 3 or higher felt that their competence was questioned when they were appointed to a leadership position. Participants who rated themselves 1-2 did not feel questioned simply because they were women. The responses suggest that a woman’s management experience may vary by industry, workplace culture or institutional policies. However, the fact that a significant number of respondents strongly agreed with this statement highlights the ongoing problem of gendered credibility issues in leadership positions.

Figure 12: Perceived limitations on access to leadership roles, n=50

Source: own data

A significant portion of the participants (scores 4-5) believe that being a woman limits their access to certain leadership roles. This situation is consistent with the glass ceiling theory, which describes the invisible barriers that can prevent women from advancing in their professional lives. The fact that some participants (scores 1-2) disagree with this suggests that access to leadership roles is not equally restricted for all women. This suggests that factors such as individual experiences, company policies and the sector play a role in shaping these perceptions. These findings support the hypothesis that gender biases and structural barriers continue to affect women's career progression in leadership positions.

Figure 13: Experiences of glass ceiling in advancing to higher management, n=50

Source: own data

According to the results, a significant number of participants (4-5 points) admit that they face invisible barriers called the “glass ceiling syndrome” that prevent them from advancing to higher management positions. This suggests that even if women have the necessary education and expertise, structural barriers still prevent them from reaching leadership roles. Meanwhile, other participants (1-2 points) do not perceive such barriers to their job growth. This means that the glass ceiling effect can vary depending on industry norms, company regulations, and individual career paths. All things considered, these findings provide support for the idea that societal biases and institutional barriers still affect women’s advancement into leadership positions.

Figure 14: Perception of leadership roles as more suitable for men, n=50

Source: own data

According to the responses given by the participants, a large majority (1-2 points) agreed that leadership roles in the workplace are generally not seen as suitable for men. The responses were relatively balanced and a significant number of participants did not agree with this statement. On the other hand, the presence of participants who agreed with this statement with (4-5 points) is undeniable and is slightly behind. In summary, the results provide mixed support for the hypothesis that social prejudices shape perceptions of gender in leadership roles. Although this prejudice seems to persist in some companies, it does not indicate that it is a widely accepted experience of all participants.

Figure 15: Perception of women leaders' competence compared to male counterparts, n=50

Source: own data

The results showed that most participants (scores 4-5) agreed that female leaders are considered to be as competent as their male counterparts in their organizations. This suggests that there is a positive perception of women in management positions and leadership in workplaces that tend not to view gender as an absolute determinant of competence. In contrast, a minority of participants (scores 1-3) either disagreed or were neutral, indicating that there is still some skepticism about female leadership. Overall, these findings provide some support for the idea that female leaders are perceived to be as competent as men, but there may still be some gender bias in certain workplace environments.

Types of Social Prejudices and Leadership Styles:

-This section tests hypothesis H3

(Gender prejudices negatively affect the perception of women managers' competencies in leadership positions.)

-Also related to Research Question 3:

(What types of social prejudices do women in leadership positions encounter throughout their careers, and how do these prejudices shape their leadership styles and decision-making processes?)

Figure 16: Exposure to the prejudice “Women are too emotional to lead”, n=50

Source: own data

The results rejected the claim that a large majority of participants experienced the stereotype that "Women are emotional and cannot lead" (1-2 points). This contradicts the claim that women are considered emotional and therefore cannot lead, and suggests that gender discrimination may be decreasing in workplaces where women in leadership positions are widely accepted. A smaller percentage of participants (4-5 points) reported experiencing this bias, suggesting that overt bias is decreasing but still present. This hypothesis is weakly supported, as the evidence does not suggest that the female leaders surveyed are exposed to this stereotype to a large extent.

Figure 17: Impact of gender-based prejudices on leadership style, n=50

Source: own data

The results are particularly concentrated on (4 points). This suggests that women in management positions agree that their leadership styles are shaped by gender biases. The conclusions can be drawn from the fact that many women may have consciously changed their leadership styles in response to society's biases and expectations. This also suggests that gender biases actively influence women's leadership actions and strategies. This is consistent with the body of research on stereotype threat and self-regulation in leadership, which shows that women often experience pressure to change their decision-making, communication, and expressions of authority to conform to male-dominated leadership standards.

Figure 18: Perceived devaluation of women’s opinions in decision-making, n=50

Source: own data

The results indicated that most participants (scores 1-2) disagreed that their opinions were not sufficiently considered in decision-making processes simply because they were women. This suggests that many workplaces may have more inclusive leadership cultures where the contributions of female managers are valued equally to their male counterparts. However, a significant number of participants also reported that their opinions were less valued. Differences in leadership styles, industry norms, and organizational cultures across organizations may explain this range of responses. Overall, the results do not appear to support the hypothesis that women’s opinions are consistently undervalued in decision-making processes, although the findings do highlight the need for more qualitative information to understand specific contexts.

Figure 19: Effort required to prove oneself as a women leader, n=50

Source: own data

The findings show that most participants (4-5 points) indicated that they have to put in more effort than their male counterparts for their current leadership positions. This means that women in leadership roles often face greater performance demands and greater scrutiny than men. This is consistent with studies on double standards in leadership, which show that women often have to make their credentials and authority more obvious in order to receive the same level of respect and recognition. The results provide compelling evidence to support the theory that gender biases have a negative impact on how women are perceived as competent leaders, increasing the burden of proof and requiring more work to establish credibility.

Obstacles Based on Social Prejudice Compared to Male Leaders:

-This section tests hypothesis H2:

(Women leaders in management positions in Türkiye face more obstacles based on social prejudice than their male counterparts.)

-Also related to Research Question 2:

(In what ways do social prejudices and the glass ceiling syndrome impact the career advancement opportunities of women in leadership positions?)

Figure 20: Perception of facing more prejudices than male leaders, n=50

Source: own data

According to the findings, a significant portion of the participants (4-5 points) think that they face more prejudice than men. This finding aligns with Role Congruity Theory, which suggests that prejudice arises when leadership traits typically associated with men are attributed to women, leading to resistance and bias against female leaders (Eagly & Karau, 2002). The presence of participants who disagree with this claim with a score of (1-2) also indicates the existence of workplaces that prioritize competence over gender in career development. All things considered; these results provide convincing evidence supporting the theory that Turkish female managers face higher barriers based on social prejudice than their male counterparts.

Figure 21: Observation of women leaders being questioned more often than men, n=50

Source: own data

According to the findings, a significant portion of the participants (4-5 points) stated that female leaders are questioned more than male leaders. According to the Role Congruence Theory

(Eagly and Karau, 2002), which argues that leadership is generally associated with masculine characteristics, prejudices against women emerge in such roles. This means that female leaders are subject to more scrutiny and suspicion in professional situations. In addition, a lower percentage of participants (1-2 points) disagreed with this view, indicating that some workplaces may evaluate male and female leaders more fairly. In summary, these results reinforce the existence of gender bias in managerial views and significantly support the idea that women in leadership roles are subject to more questioning and suspicion than male leaders.

Figure 22: Perception of leadership decisions being taken less seriously, n=50

Source: own data

The results show that most of the participants (1-2 points) consider the decisions they make as leaders to be taken as seriously as those of male leaders. This means that in many companies, the power and decision-making processes of female managers are valued at the same level as their male counterparts. On the other hand, there are participants (4-5 points) who believe that the decisions they make in a leadership position are not taken seriously. This shows that gender biases still affect women's decision-making processes in some workplaces. The findings do not provide convincing evidence to support the theory that the decisions that female leaders can make are taken less seriously than those of their male counterparts. The majority of the participants believe that their authority is recognized in their workplaces.

Figure 23: Extra effort made to be taken seriously as leader, n=50

Source: own data

The results show that participants overwhelmingly (4-5 points) stated that they put in extra effort to be taken seriously as leaders. This result suggests that female leaders are often subject to greater pressure to have their authority recognized than their male counterparts. The findings provide compelling evidence to support the theory that women must work harder to be taken seriously as leaders due to societal prejudices and must strive to achieve work-life balance. Research on double standards in leadership suggests that women often need to demonstrate higher levels of competence and aggression in order to be recognized and taken seriously on equal footing with male leaders.

Figure 24: Recognition of women leaders' achievements compared to male leaders, n=50

Source: own data

According to the findings, a significant percentage of participants (1-2 points) think that the achievements of female leaders are not valued and appreciated as much as those of men. This means that there are still gender biases in the evaluation and recognition of leadership achievements, and that men are likely to receive more credit for similar achievements. However, in some contexts, merit-based recognition may be more balanced, as some participants (4-5 points) think that the achievements of women are equally recognized. Overall, these results reinforce the existence of systemic biases in professional recognition and appreciation and provide moderate to strong support for the hypothesis that the achievements of female leaders are not as well-known as the achievements of their male counterparts.

Analysis of Solutions, Institutional Policies, and Recommendations:

-This section tests hypothesis H1:

(Glass ceiling syndrome and social prejudice have negative effects on women's rise to management positions in Türkiye.)

-This section tests hypothesis H2:

(Women leaders in management positions in Türkiye face more obstacles based on social prejudice than their male counterparts.)

-Also related to Research Question 2 and Question 3:

(In what ways do social prejudices and the glass ceiling syndrome impact the career advancement opportunities of women in leadership positions?)

(What types of social prejudices do women in leadership positions encounter throughout their careers, and how do these prejudices shape their leadership styles and decision-making processes?)

This section will examine open-ended comments on the suggestions participants have for increasing access to leadership roles for women, institutional policies and measures to increase female leaders, and steps to be taken to increase female representation in leadership roles across Türkiye. Since the responses were qualitative, thematic methods were used to analyze recurring keywords, suggestions, and tactics. The most frequently mentioned suggestions and institutional policies will be highlighted, and the responses will be divided into main headings according to their content. The aim is to help shed light on ways organizations, society, and policymakers can support the growth of an inclusive leadership environment for women.

Question 1: *"What are the most important factors that would facilitate women's access to leadership positions?"*

When the most frequently repeated keywords were analyzed based on the participants' answers.

Policies and laws pertaining to gender equality:

- Putting in place equitable hiring and promotion procedures.
- Guaranteeing equal compensation for equal labor.
- Bolstering anti-discrimination legislation.

Education and the Development of Leadership:

- Extending mentorship and leadership development initiatives.
- Promoting sponsorship and networking possibilities.
- Encouraging women to take up decision-making responsibilities.

Organizational and Cultural Change:

- Bringing attention to gender disparities in the selection of leaders.
- Supporting laws that give women a work-life balance.
- Supporting masculine allies in the fight for gender equality.

The results indicate that women's leadership opportunities are still restricted by societal biases and institutional constraints. These issues can be lessened and gender-equal leadership participation can be encouraged by putting in place gender-inclusive policies, leadership development programs, and cultural changes.

Keywords: *Equal, Support, Education, Policy*

Question 2: *"What organizational policies could support women leaders?"*

When the most frequently repeated keywords were analyzed based on the participants' answers.

Equal Opportunity and Anti-Discrimination Policies:

- Ensure fairness through gender-blind hiring and promotion procedures.
- Strengthen anti-discrimination policies in workplaces.
- Equal pay policies to reduce the gender pay gap.

Mentoring and Leadership Development Programs:

- Create sponsorship and mentoring initiatives for female employees.
- Provide special leadership training for the professional development of female managers.
- Create networking sites to develop networks.

Work-Life Balance and Family Support Policies:

- Offer remote work options and flexible working hours to help balance family and professional commitments.
- Provide financial assistance for in-company childcare facilities and crèches for working mothers.
- Maternity leave policies should be improved, and paternity leave should be provided to support shared parenting.

The findings imply that organizational policies should address gender equality, leadership development, and work-life balance to support women in leadership positions. The focus on flexible work hours, childcare services, and maternity leave highlights the specific challenges working mothers face in advancing their careers. Addressing these concerns can help alleviate structural barriers and improve female representation in leadership.

Keywords: *Equality, Flexibility, Work-Family Balance, Maternity*

Question 3: *"What societal changes are needed to increase women's leadership in Türkiye?"*

When the most frequently repeated keywords were analyzed based on the participants' answers.

Gender Perception and Cultural Change:

- Eliminate cultural gender norms that allow men to be perceived as absolute leaders.
- Raise awareness of gender equality in leadership.
- Encourage media to portray female leaders as role models.

Equal Employment and Education Opportunities:

- Support early gender equality education initiatives.
- Encouraging greater female participation in traditionally male-dominated sectors such as business and STEM.
- Provide women with equal access to opportunities for professional development.

Reforms in Law and Institutions:

- Implement stronger legal safeguards against discrimination and mobbing in the workplace.
- Establish gender quotas for leadership positions in both the public and private sectors.
- Advocate for work-life balance laws that help women advance their careers.

The results show that women in leadership positions are still affected by institutional injustices and gender-based biases. Legislative changes, educational changes and cultural change must all be combined to solve these problems and create an atmosphere where women can equally assume leadership roles.

Likert Scale Questions: Perceptions of Women in Leadership:

-This section tests hypothesis H1:

(Glass ceiling syndrome and social prejudice have negative effects on women's rise to management positions in Türkiye.)

-This section tests hypothesis H2:

(Women leaders in management positions in Türkiye face more obstacles based on social prejudice than their male counterparts.)

-This section tests hypothesis H3:

(Gender prejudices negatively affect the perception of women managers' competencies in leadership positions.)

Figure 25: Perception of women’s leadership effectiveness, n=50

Source: own data

Based on the results of this Likert-scale question, there is strong evidence to support the idea that women are as capable of leading as men. 92% of participants agreed with this statement with a high rating of 5, while 8% rated it a 4. The average score given was (4.92). Interestingly, no participant rated this statement as 1, 2, or 3, indicating neither disagreement nor neutrality. Women believe that women are in fact just as effective leaders as their male counterparts. Women are thought to be able to implement effective management strategies and manage teams effectively when they enter a leadership position. The strong agreement suggests that participants accept women’s leadership qualities, even if there are still institutional barriers to implementation, although these data do not fully assess the barriers.

Figure 26: Gender is not important for leadership in the business world, n=50

Source: own data

The overwhelming majority of participants (88% or 44 participants) chose "5-Strongly Agree" when answering this item. Six participants or 12% chose "4-Agree" makes Average rating (4.50). None of the participants checked the "Undecided", "Disagree" or "Strongly Disagree" boxes. The results of this vote demonstrate the belief that special support, mentoring programs and new policies should be developed at the institutional level in order for women leaders to become more visible and successful in their working lives and in the business world. The findings indicate that institutions should take more active roles in promoting women's leadership. At the same time, these results emphasize the need for strategic and sustainable support mechanisms to overcome the structural obstacles women leaders face.

Figure 27: Women leaders face more obstacle than male leaders, n=50

Source: own data

The majority of participants (68%) indicated that they strongly agreed with this statement by giving it a score of 5 out of 5, 10% gave a score of 4, and 20% gave a score of 3. This distribution shows that there is a high awareness among participants that female leaders face more obstacles than their male counterparts. The average score of 4.44 also shows that this view is generally supported. This finding directly supports the second hypothesis of the study (*Women leaders in management positions in Türkiye face more social prejudice-based obstacles than their male counterparts*). This question is also related to Research Question 2: *In what ways do social prejudices and the glass ceiling syndrome impact the career advancement opportunities of women in leadership positions?*

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to examine how glass ceiling syndrome and social prejudice affect women's advancement in leadership roles in Türkiye. The main aim of the study was to investigate and clarify the obstacles that women leaders face due to social prejudices and gender-based discrimination in the workplace. Important insights into the challenges women face when assuming leadership positions and how these challenges affect their experiences were obtained from the data collected through a structured survey. The results show that gender-based discrimination is a common occurrence for women in leadership roles and contributes to their ability to advance in their careers. The prevalence of glass ceiling syndrome and social prejudice is evident when the majority of participants reported that they faced invisible barriers that prevented them from advancing to higher-level management positions when their responses and evaluations were examined. Furthermore, the study found that the perspective of women's leadership potential is still affected by social prejudices based on gender norms. These prejudices lead to doubts about women's abilities in managerial roles and unequal recognition of their achievements. The study also highlighted subtle differences in participants' perspectives on leadership in the workplace. While some participants reported there are improvements in gender equality, however, a significant number of them reported prejudice, invisible barriers, and stereotypes. Additionally, open-ended questions helped generate qualitative data on the challenges faced by women leaders and the proposed solutions to these challenges.

A study with more participants and a larger sample size can be conducted to make it more specific by focusing on different sectors in order to support and build on the current study. Furthermore, conducting a long-term study will provide researchers with a greater understanding of how attitudes towards women's leadership have changed over time. The effectiveness of organizational practices that aim to carry out inclusive activities that support gender equality in leadership and create plans and projects in this context can be the subject of further research. In conclusion, this study highlights the ongoing challenges that Turkish women leaders face in their careers despite the ongoing plans targeting development in this regard and the need for continuous efforts to eliminate barriers based on social prejudice and glass ceiling. Companies, society and legislators should work together to address these issues and promote an inclusive and equitable workplace.

Evaluation: A mixed approach was used through these two data analysis methods. The methodology was designed to ensure comprehensive data collection and analysis. The

responses to the open-ended questions in the survey questionnaire allowed for qualitative data collection, while the responses to the Likert-type and scoring questions allowed for quantitative data collection for the study. This method allowed for the study subjects and hypotheses to be examined from various perspectives. Although the objectives of the study were effectively met, some limitations should be noted. First, although the sample size was sufficient for the initial findings, generalizations cannot be made to all Turkish women leaders. Also, the use of self-reported data increases the possibility of bias, as participants may interpret or experience prejudice and discrimination differently. Despite these drawbacks, the findings provide context-specific insights relevant to the Turkish sociocultural context, while also being consistent with the existing literature on gender bias in leadership.

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Appendix

The following section contains the questions presented in the survey conducted as part of this research study. These questions were designed to assess the impact of gender-based discrimination, social prejudices, and the glass ceiling syndrome on women's career development and leadership experiences in Türkiye.

Survey Questions:

1. Demographic Information

- Age
- Education level
- Sector you work in (public, private, NGO, etc.)
- Current position (e.g., middle manager, senior manager)
- Number of years spent at the management level
- Female manager rate in the institution you work for (roughly)

2. Gender-Based Discrimination and Career Trajectories

- To what extent has your gender negatively affected your career advancement?
- To what extent have you faced more barriers to promotion compared to your male colleagues?
- To what extent have you experienced explicit or implicit gender-based discrimination in your workplace?
- To what extent have you felt that your competence was questioned when appointed to a leadership position just because you are a woman?

3. Social Prejudices and Glass Ceiling Syndrome

- To what extent do you think being a woman has limited your access to certain leadership roles?
- To what extent have you experienced invisible barriers (glass ceiling) that limit your advancement to higher management positions?

- To what extent do you think leadership roles are generally perceived as more suitable for men in your workplace?
- To what extent do you think women leaders are considered as competent as their male counterparts in your organization?

4. Types of Social Prejudices and Leadership Styles

- To what extent have you been exposed to prejudices like “women are too emotional to lead”?
- To what extent have gender-based prejudices influenced how you shape your leadership style?
- To what extent have you felt that your opinions were less valued in decision-making processes because you are a woman?
- To what extent have you had to work harder to prove yourself as a woman leader?

5. Social Prejudice-Based Obstacles vs Male Counterparts

- To what extent do you face more prejudices than male leaders?
- To what extent do you observe that women leaders are questioned more often than male leaders?
- To what extent are the decisions you make as a leader taken less seriously than those of male leaders?
- To what extent have you made an extra effort to be taken seriously as a leader?
- To what extent are women leaders’ achievements appreciated as much as male leaders’ achievements?

6. Solutions, Institutional Policies, and Recommendations

- What are the most important factors that would facilitate women’s access to leadership positions?
- What organizational policies could support women leaders?
- What societal changes are needed to increase women’s leadership in Turkey?

7. Likert Scale Questions (1: Strongly Disagree – 5: Strongly Agree)

- Women are as effective leaders as men.
- Gender does not matter for leadership in business.
- Organizations should create special support programs for women leaders.
- Women leaders face more obstacles than male leaders.